

Studies on Chelation of Alcohol Soluble Soil Organic Matter Fraction with Metals

M. ADHIKARI, G. CHAKRAVORTY & G. C. HAZRA

Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University

Received 2 July 1970; revised MSS received 13 April 1971

Studies were conducted to investigate the interactions between certain bivalent and trivalent metallic cations and alcohol soluble humic acid (Hy.A.) fraction of soil humic acid isolated from alluvial soil of West Bengal by electrometric titrations and absorption spectroscopy. Discontinuous conductometric titrations showed the formation of more than one complex. Potentiometric titrations in presence of metallic cations indicated the formation of Hy.A-metal complexes. The order of the magnitude of pH drop of Hy.A. on addition of metallic cations was found to be $Ni^{2+} < Zn^{2+} < Cu^{2+}$ and $Fe^{2+} < Fe^{3+} < Al^{3+}$.

Absorption spectroscopy showed the formation of complexes of different molal compositions at different pH values.

The stable compound formation of soil organic matter with metals has been demonstrated by several workers. Khanna and Stevenson¹, Schnitzer and Skinner² after studying such interactions extensively, agree to the point of chelation. It is now believed that ion exchange, surface adsorption, chelation, coagulation and peptization processes are involved in these reactions^{2,9,10,11}. The purpose of this paper is to provide information on the interactions of different metal ions with the alcohol soluble humic acid (Hy.A) fraction of soil organic matter (O.M.) which contain quinone groups in the main molecule and the presence of nitrogen is due to secondary combination with amino acid or protein. Different functional groups like $-NH_2$, OH (phenolic and alcoholic), $-COOH$ etc., are present in this fraction⁶. Various physical methods like electrometric titrations, absorption spectroscopy etc. are employed in present studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

Organic matter was extracted and fractionated from alluvial surface soil (10–15 cm, depth) from Chinsura, West Bengal, by the standard procedure⁶. The Hy.A fraction was subjected to repeated resin (IR-120) treatment to decrease its ash content to the minimum (0.01%) in order to get sure that the ligand is free from metal ion.

Conductometric titrations : In a number of stoppered 25 ml conical flasks known amount of Hy.A. and increasing amounts of different salt solutions *viz.*, $CuSO_4$, $NiSO_4$, $ZnSO_4$, $FeCl_3$ and $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ were added. The total volume was made to 10 ml. The contents of the flasks were shaken for 8 hrs and allowed to equilibrate overnight. After equilibrium, conductance of these solutions were measured using a Leeds-Northrup Conductivity Bridge

in a thermostat maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$. Conductometric titrations of Hy.A with NaOH was carried out and also Hy.A+metal combinations with NaOH.

Potentiometric titrations : In one set of experiment, to 1.715×10^{-7} moles of Hy.A 10 ml distilled water and 2 ml of (N) KCl solution were added. NaOH (0.915 N/100) was added slowly in 0.1 ml increments and corresponding pH value of the solution was noted with Cambridge pH meter at 30° equipped with Cambridge Glass Electrode and a saturated Calomel Electrode with an aqueous agar agar salt bridge. Similarly 1.715×10^{-7} moles Hy.A was titrated in presence of varying concentration MSO_4 [M = Cu, Ni or Zn] solutions and the metal salt solutions with NaOH solution. In another set 0.009803×10^{-7} moles of Hy.A, in presence of 0.009803×10^{-7} moles of FeCl_3 and $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ were titrated with 0.261 (N/100) NaOH solution as also FeCl_3 and $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ solution with NaOH.

Spectrophotometric method : For this 1 to 9 ml aliquots of Hy.A. and 9 to 1 ml aliquots of CuSO_4 , NiSO_4 and FeCl_3 solutions were pipetted into 10 ml volumetric flasks and the volume was made to the mark with double distilled water. The pH of these solutions were adjusted to 4. In a separate set of experiment pH was adjusted to 5.5 by dilute NaOH solution. These solutions were taken in 25 ml stoppered conical flasks and shaken for 2 hr and kept for 4 hr to attain equilibrium. Optical density of different preparations were measured by a Beckmann Spectrophotometer at 400 nm which was found to be the region of maximum absorption of Hy.A-metal complexes.

Flocculation Method : The minimum amount of metallic cations required to coagulate Hy.A were determined as follows :

To 1 ml solution of different salt solutions *viz.*, CuSO_4 , NiSO_4 and FeCl_3 in a series of stoppered conical flasks increasing volumes of Hy.A (4.25 m.moles/lit) were added. With two separate sets pH were adjusted to 4.0 and 5.50 respectively and in each case volume was made to 12 ml. The contents of the flasks were shaken vigorously for 8 hr and kept for 24 hr at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$. After 24 hr each system was checked for flocculation. The minimum amount of Hy.A required to prevent flocculation of the metal salts expressed in terms of molal ratios were taken as a measure of complexing power².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The average molecular wt. of Hy.A, as extracted and fractionated from Chinsura Sub-soil, was found to be 1020.⁶ In the present discussions the results are expressed on this basis.

Conductometric titrations : Instantaneous conductometric titration curves of Hy.A with different metal salts *viz.*, CuSO_4 , NiSO_4 , ZnSO_4 , FeCl_3 etc. are continuous in nature indicating no complex formation. But on allowing the reaction mixture to equilibrate, two breaks are noticed Fig. [1(a) and 1(b)] corresponding to the formation of two different complexes.

The mole ratio of the first complex is $\text{Hy.A}/\text{M}^{2+} = 0.5 : 1$ [$\text{M}^{2+} = \text{Cu}^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} or Zn^{2+}] but the ratio for second complex changes to 0.20 : 1 for $\text{Hy.A}/\text{Ni}^{2+}$, 0.19 : 1 for $\text{Hy.A}/\text{Cu}^{2+}$

and 0.22 : 1 for Hy.A/ Zn^{2+} . The mole ratio with trivalent metal ion *viz.*, Hy.A/ Fe^{3+} changes from 1.36 : 1 to 0.90 : 1. Fig. 1(c).

During the titration of Hy.A with metal ions the conductance of solution increases after the formation of the complex. This might be due to the fact that complex formation does not always result in decreased electrical conductance, since there is chance of increasing the conductance of the media by suitable interactions whereupon highly conducting

ionic species are resulted due to complex formation. Not only a strong electrolyte is produced from weak electrolyte but one of the ions formed may be highly mobile *e.g.*, H^+ . The sharp rise in conductance after the formation of the complex may thus be due to the liberation of such mobile hydrogen ions to form hydroxylated metal Hy.A complexes. The fall in conductance as noticed in Fig. 1(a) and 1(c) may possibly be due to conversion of the hydroxylated metal Hy.A complex to metal Hy.A complex under the influence of excess metal ions.

During the titration with NaOH solution the initial conductance of different metal-Hy.A combinations are greater than Hy.A alone [Fig. 1(d) and 1(e)]. It may possibly be due to weak acid behaviour of Hy.A having low degree of ionization. During interaction with metal ions the conductance increases considerably due to formation of strong electrolyte

and subsequent liberation of hydrogen ions. This behaviour may be expected from the nature of the equilibrium depicted below whereupon hydrogen ions are produced as a result of chelation.

Furthermore, the conductance difference between these curves increases as the solution becomes more alkaline indicating that the complexes are more stable in basic media. The observed stabilities of different metal-Hy.A combinations are as follows

and

The fact that titration with NaOH resulting in a low conductance when the chelate is formed may be visualised from the following reactions

The large anion MA_n would be expected to have a lower conductance than the smaller anion A^- since the latter is extensively hydrolyzed in an aqueous solution to give the highly conducting ions.

It is to be noted that there is no initial decrease in conductance on addition of NaOH to metal-Hy.A (fig. 1(d, e)) instead there is continual increase in conductance, possibly this is due to buffering action of the ligand, or the H^+ liberated is small in comparison to first addition of NaOH, as a result the inflection point is missed.

Potentiometric titrations : Titration data [shown in Fig. 2(a)–2(c)] of Hy.A with added metallic cations indicate the formation of stable metal complexes. Titration curves of organic ligand in presence of metal salts show considerable drop in $p\text{H}$. Although metal salt solutions are fairly acidic, the initial drop in $p\text{H}$ in the titration curves of Hy.A-metal combinations are not due to free metal ions as the free metallic cations interact with the functional sites of Hy.A liberating protons. That the drop in $p\text{H}$ of these solutions is due to these liberated protons is evident from the fact that at no stage of titration turbidity associated with metallic hydroxide formation can be detected under the influence of excess alkali. The formation of metal hydroxide is however indicated by inflections in curve 2(c). No such inflections appear in curve 2(a) and 2(b) representing mixture of Hy.A-metal ions which supports complex formation. Martell and Calvin³ point out that greater the tendency of metals to combine with a given chelating agent greater is the $p\text{H}$ drop. Such drop in $p\text{H}$ by the addition of metal salts to Hy.A solution varies markedly with metal ions. The change in $p\text{H}$ on titration of the Hy.A in presence of various metallic cations follows the order $\text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Zn}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+}$ ($< p\text{H}$ 7.5) and the sequence is in general agreement with that reported earlier^{4,8} and is found to follow the Irving-Williams stability series⁷.

As said before the soil organic matter contains different functional groups, the formation of chelates are, thus, confirmed from the potentiometric studies.

The stabilities of Ferric, Ferrous, Aluminium Hy.A complexes follow the order $Fe^{2+} < Fe^{3+} < Al^{3+}$. The marked pH change in the titration with Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} in comparison to other metals indicate the greater tendency for these cations to form complexes with Hy.A. From titration curve of Hy.A with NaOH no second ionization of weaker acidic groups has been noticed but in presence of different metal ions such ionizations are prominent [Fig. 2(a)]. It is therefore evident that these weaker acidic groups like phenolic

hydroxyls take part in reaction with metal ions producing free hydrogen ions. As more and more such groups interact with metal ions possibility of the metal-Hy.A complexes increases followed by marked pH change Fig. 2(a). The interactions of carboxylic and phenolic hydroxyl groups of Hy.A. with metal ions thus appears to be similar to iron salicylic acid type of interaction.

In order to get an idea about the mechanism of metal-Hy.A. interactions the number of protons released by NaOH during the titration of Hy.A. and mixture of Hy.A.-metal salts are assessed in Tables 1 (a & b).

TABLE 1(a)

pH	Number of protons released from Hy.A/mole of base added
6.5	—
7.0	1.37
7.5	2.05
8.0	2.60
8.5	3.43
9.0	5.10

From Table 1(a) it is evident that at *pH* 7.0, approximately one -COOH group has been titrated similarly at *pH* 7.5, two and at *pH* 8.0, approximately three and at *pH* 9.0, two phenolic hydroxyl groups have been titrated in addition to the three -COOH groups.

The difference of protons set free from metal Hy.A. combinations [Table 1(b)] can be rationalized by writing the following simplified equations, taking Cu-Hy.A. as an example (*R* denote the Hy.A. molecule without three -COOH groups).

TABLE 1(b)

<i>pH</i>	Number of protons released from Hy.A./mole of metal added							
	Fe-Hy.A. complex	Al-Hy.A. complex	Cu complex		Ni complex		Zn complex	
			Low	High	Low	High	Low	High
6.5	1.13	0.85	1.50	0.68	0.27	—	0.03	—
7.0	1.51	1.52	1.58	1.10	0.48	—	0.15	—
7.5	2.02	2.16	1.75	1.24	0.50	—	0.46	0.2
8.0	2.77	3.09	2.10	1.28	0.58	0.16	1.40	1.94
8.5	3.02	3.72	2.10	1.40	0.58	0.20	4.10	3.80
9.0	—	—	—	—	0.75	1.04	—	—
9.5	—	—	—	—	1.70	—	—	—

When no Cu-salt is added

3 protons are released.

When Cu salt is added

3 protons are released.

4 protons are released.

5 protons are released.

Data in Table 1(b), Fig. 2(b) indicate that interaction between Hy.A and lesser amount of Cu^{2+} ions (2.60×10^{-7} moles) produces an unstable combination which decomposes completely at *pH* 8.1. But in presence of higher amount of Cu^{2+} ions (7.28×10^{-7} moles), the reaction proceeds according to equation (c) within the *pH* range 6.5 to 8.5. The data in the same table reveal that reaction between Hy.A and Ni^{2+} ions (2.66×10^{-7} moles) proceeds according to equation (b) upto *pH* 8.5. At *pH* 9.1, hydroxylated Ni-Hy.A. complex results according to equation (c) and the complex breaks apart at *pH* 9.5. In presence of increasing concentration of Ni^{2+} ions (6.85×10^{-7} moles), similar reactions occur. The number of proton set free/mole of Zn^{2+} is much less than unity upto *pH* 7.5, indicating the probability of the

reaction according to equation (b). The decomposition of the complex occurs at pH 8.0. These interactions remain unaffected in presence of higher concentration (5.92×10^{-7} moles) of Zn^{2+} ions.

In case of metal Hy.A complexes the number of protons released decreases on increasing the concentration of metal ions indicating that the newly added metallic cations react with the co-ordinating groups *viz.*, $-NH_2$ etc. of the ligand and hence no more protons are liberated. The stabilities of these complexes in presence of increasing concentration of metal ions, as evident from proton release data [Table 1(b)] thus increase due to co-ordination bond formation between metal ions and the functional groups of the ligand.

2 ml OF 0.01M METAL IONS

The release of approximately one proton upto pH 7.0, during the interaction of Hy.A. and trivalent metal ions *viz.*, Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} suggest hydroxylated metal Hy.A. complex formation. The predominant species at this pH range is $M(OH)^{+}_2$ [$M = Fe$ and Al] which

form electrovalent bond with one negatively charged $-\text{COOH}$ group of the ligand. At pH 7.5, the proton release data indicate the interaction of $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2^+$ species with one $-\text{COOH}$ group present in Hy.A. molecule. At pH 8.0 both Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} complexes break apart.

Spectrophotometric studies: Absorption curves of 0.588×10^{-3} moles of Hy.A. and equimolecular mixture of 0.588×10^{-3} moles of Hy.A. and Nickel ion between 400 to 600 $\text{m}\mu$ are shown in Fig. 3(a). The optical density (O.D.) of Fe-Hy.A. is higher than Hy.A. in all wavelengths. The highest difference is obtained at the wavelength 400 nm. Consequently 400 $\text{m}\mu$ is chosen as a suitable wavelength for all further works. Plot of O.D. vs. concentration for organic matter follows straight lines corresponding to pH values 4.0 and 5.50 at the wavelength 400 nm. These plots were used to calculate Y values at both the pH 4.0 and 5.50. Since the optical densities of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Fe^{3+} salts even at the highest

concentrations used in these experiments were less than 0.01, these values were neglected in calculating Y values. Job plots⁵ of metal Hy.A. show that the mole ratio of Hy.A./Cu is 0.5/1 at pH 4.0 and changes to 0.25/1 at pH 5.5. The same ratio for Hy.A./Ni is 0.99/1 at pH 4.0 and changes to 0.25/1 at pH 5.5. The ratio for Hy.A./ Fe^{3+} is 1.38/1 at pH 4.0 and changes to 1/1 at pH 5.5.

At lower pH value although two moles of Cu are complexed/mole of Hy.A., approximately 1 mole of Ni is complexed/mole of ligand. Due to amphoteric nature Cu^{2+} reacts with the functional groups of the ligand as $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, but such hydrolysis is suppressed in case of Ni and possibly Ni^{2+} ions react with the functional groups of the ligand and consequently number of metal complexed/mole of Hy.A. decreases. When pH of the solution increases the amount of hydroxylated metallic species *e.g.* $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$ are considerably higher *i.e.*, more $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$ [$\text{M} = \text{Cu}$ or Ni] ions react with the ligand. As a result the number of moles of

metal complexed/mole of Hy.A. increases to four. At pH 5.5, both Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} undergo hydrolysis to produce $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$ or $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})^+$ species. As these hydroxylated metals react with the functional groups of the ligand no difference in the number of metal complexed/mole of Hy.A. can be observed.

Complexing Power of Hy.A. for Ferric Iron and Copper by Flocculation Method : Data for complexing power of Hy.A. for Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} show 1.20 moles of Fe^{3+} and 2.0 moles of Cu^{2+} reacting with 1 mole of Hy.A.

The authors are grateful to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee and Dr. S. Aditya of this University for their kind interest and helpful discussions in the progress of the work and to C.S.I.R. for the financial assistance.

REFERENCES

1. S. S. Khanna and F. J. Stevenson, *Soil Sci.*, 1962, **93**, 298.
2. M. Schnitzer and S. I. M. Skinner, *Soil Sci.*, 1963, **96**, 86.
3. A. E. Martell and M. Calvin. Prentice-Hall Inc., New York (1952).
4. S. U. Khan, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1969, **33**, 851.
5. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
6. Chabbi Datta, D.Phil. thesis, Calcutta University, 1968.
7. H. M. N. H. Irving and R. T. P. Williams, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.
8. R. S. Beckwith, *Austral J. Agr. Res.*, 1955, **6**, 685.
9. L. N. Aleksandrova, *Soviet Soil Sci.*, 1967, **7**, 903.
10. F. E. Broadbent and J. B. Ott, *Soil Sci.*, 1957, **83**, 419.
11. M. M. Kononova, *Soil Organic Matter*, Pergamon Press, New York (1966).